

Weddell Sea Observatory of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Change – WOBEC Standard

Operating Procedures

Technical Documentation

December 2025

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Versions

Met opmerkingen [1]: please remember to credit megan for this sop because she helped a ton

Date	Comment	Responsible	Approved
17/03/2025	First draft	N. Van den Steen	
12/12/2025	Formatting	N. Van den Steen	

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1 Description and Responsibilities

Labeling samples is essential for maintaining data integrity, ensuring traceability, and preventing errors in scientific research and environmental monitoring. Proper labeling allows researchers to accurately associate samples with their collection details, such as date, location, and methodology, which is crucial for reproducibility and meaningful analysis. It also helps in organizing and managing samples throughout processing, storage, and analysis, reducing the risk of mix-ups or contamination. Unclear labeling renders deployments useless.

Before the cruise, each team should appoint a member to take on the role of data manager, responsible for ensuring that all sample identifiers are **unique** and that metadata and data templates are correctly completed. If a new sample identifier is assigned to a sample, the old sample identifier must be recorded in data sheet to ensure traceability.

A global data manager will oversee the work of the team data managers and ensure compliance with expedition data standards. All label IDs must be linked to their data sheet to maintain traceability throughout the expedition.

2 Identifier vs Physical Label

First a distinction needs to be made between the *identifier* and the *physical label*.

Identifier is a unique code linking the physical sample with the metadata and completed data templates. Subsamples are linked through the parent identifier in the template.

The **physical label** contains the sample's identifier along with additional human-readable information. While well-designed labels improve sample management, they are not strictly necessary for data integrity.

3 Labeling: identifier and label

Before the cruise, each team's data manager must **prepare** stickers with sample identifiers and labels. Every sample must have a **unique identifier** to ensure traceability.

3.1 Identifier Format

The format of the identifier is:

[EXPEDITION_NUMBER]_[6_CHAR_CAT_ID]_[5_DIGIT_SEQUENTIAL_NUMB]

Met opmerkingen [2]: Can we put this at the front, actually applies to all SOP person responsible should be the first thing mentioned. see how it was done for the biopole COOKbook and the nansen legacy SOP's

Met opmerkingen [3]: I think this could be discussed. I would use wording like prepare labels. Also we should think about labelling digital files...

Met opmerkingen [4]: What do you mean with labeling digital files?

- **EXPEDITION_NUMBER:** Assigned by the coordinating institution (e.g., for WOBE, the expedition code is PS152). The EXPEDITION_NUMBER guarantees uniqueness of the sample **between expeditions**.
- **6_CHAR_CAT_ID:** Each team picks its own code(s) with a fixed width of 6 characters, left-padded with 'x'. If the codes are decided, they will be listed in this SOP.
- **5_DIGIT_SEQUENTIAL_NUMB:** A unique 5-digit, zero-padded numeric code for each sample within the group. The sequential number is only to be used for a single sample. This guarantees the uniqueness of the sample identifier **within** the group.
- **Example:** PS152_xxMRMT_00010

3.2 Label Information

Each label **must** include:

- **Identifier:** Essential for linking the physical sample to data and metadata.

Labels should also contain the following information if space permits:

- **Station number:** Please use the **assigned** station number as this will be used to derived sampling event information from the ship's log.
- Sampling gear and other parameters to help identified the sample.

4 Labeling Best Practices

Depending on the type of labeling materials the team has access to, the approach on labeling may differ.

4.1 Recommended Labeling Materials

Waterproof Paper (for handwritten labels)

- Use Rite in the Rain waterproof paper or similar synthetic paper.
- Write with (mechanical) pencils (0.5mm HB or 2B lead)

Printed Paper Labels (if laminated before departure)

- Use laser-printed labels on waterproof paper and laminate them.
- Attach securely with waterproof adhesive or tape.

Tape for Additional Protection

- Transparent tape (e.g., Scotch Extreme or Cryo-Tape) can be used to cover labels and improve durability.

Met opmerkingen [5]: imagining things here because I have absolutely no idea what type of materials everyone has access to.

Met opmerkingen [6]: our musuesm people should be able to provide better guidelines, or they should be availble online.

Met opmerkingen [7]: Asked some people from the collections some information. There exists an ISO, but everyone has their own preferences. Big difference between short and longterm preservation.

Met opmerkingen [8]: check with Martina

4.2 Label Placement Strategy

The placement of labels depends on the type of container and the environmental risks.

Labels should be positioned for both **visibility** and **durability**:

- Attach a label to the **outside** and **top** of the container.
This makes it easier to find samples in a storage box.
- Place a duplicate label **inside** the container, if feasible.
The outer label may fade, become detached, or be damaged by cold, moisture, or ethanol exposure.
- For vials or small containers, attach a label on the **lid**.
This allows for easy identification when searching through multiple vials in a rack or box.

All labels must be recorded in the team's data sheet.